

ACADEMIC STRESS AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS SUICIDE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SCIENCE AND ARTS INTERMEDIATE STUDENTS

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Abstract

A lot of work has been done on finding out the role of stress in our lives. Stress plays a very crucial role in our daily functioning. If a person is under stress due to anything, it is going to affect his or her social or occupational functioning. Stress can manifest in various forms, including physical stress, social stress, occupational stress, and academic stress. Stress results in many adverse consequences, including frustration, conflicts, suicide, and other destructive behaviors. This research aimed to compare the science and arts intermediate students in terms of academic stress and attitude towards suicide. Data was collected from 120 intermediate students in two groups, as science and arts groups, to check the differences in the level of stress and attitude towards suicide through the Educational Stress Scale for adolescents (ESSA) and the attitude towards suicide scale (ATTS). The results of the independent sample t-test indicated that science students would have a higher level of academic stress and attitude towards suicide than arts students. It was also indicated that there was significant positive relationship between academic stress and attitude towards suicide.

INTRODUCTION

Stress plays vital role in our daily lives and its role in education department is also becoming very important. A widespread study on stress has deduced the results which conclude that this specific topic should be studied more in future (Adil & Parveen, 2022; Barbayannis et al., 2022). Stress is defined by Lazarus as a state of being anxious when things exceed one's coping abilities (Obbarius et al., 2021). When this anxiety and pressure become extended and out of control, then it initiates helplessness,

hopelessness, depression, sadness and stress (Al-Masry, 2022).

Stress has three main types. Firstly, its eustress which is a good stress and in any condition a person feels relaxing, i.e., falling in love is a good example of eustress. Then, second is eustress which is neither good stress and nor bad. A person has no sensory response. News of an earthquake in a remote corner of the world might be an example of this stress. Then comes the third which is distress, an actual bad and

known to be simply as stress. All kinds of stress have costs and benefits and needs to be checked properly (Pluut et al., 2022).

One of the types of distress is “Academic stress,” which is currently under discussion in this research. Academics can be defined as conducting different tests, writing articles or finalizing different assignments and projects. In short, academics measure what a person has learned in the past (Shan & Hu, 2025). A college student faces diverse categories of stressors during his or her educational career like professional pursuits, academic deadlines, exams, papers and projects, school loans, make financial arrangements, lifestyle behavior, acquaintances, friendly relationships, peer sets and peer pressure (like drugs, outing and alcohol), knowing about sexuality (Barbayannis et al., 2022).

Deng et al (2022) indicated that a lot to identify the signs and effects of stressors that are experienced by intermediate students in higher institutions. Similarly, different stressors related to educational atmosphere and pressure were also explored. It was deduced that bad result, weak performance in studies, grind of college work, insufficient requirements, high strength in class rooms and insecurity of getting job after graduating result in tension among students. Stress related to academics have long been investigated as researchers have recognized competitions, too many assignments, family tassels, bad interaction with teachers and students, lack of pocket money are major stressors and large number of students in lecture halls and lack of resources are also taken as major stressors which results in health-related problems (Alshammari, 2022).

The burden of doing well in the test according to the given time makes academic environment very tense (Alshareef et al., 2025). This kind of situation is harmful regarding the social relationships with in university and outside since there occur dispute in social setup of life and its effects are far reaching as the person’s life regarding the achievement of aims suffers. If the University administrator knows the causes of student’s stress, he will be able to keep the check and balance of the factors responsible for student’s stress (Senter, 2023). Academic commitments, financial crises, and lack of the ability to manage time, and procrastination actually cause stress and when a person perceives this stress as

negative and becomes unmanageable, then it affects both health and performance (Deng et al., 2022).

The signs and symptoms of stress have been investigated and found that loss of energy, taking overdose drugs, out of control blood pressure, feeling sadness, increase or decrease in appetite, distractibility, agitation, irritability, worries and different tensions and angst are the main symptoms of stress (Chu, et al., 2024). These symptoms have dreadful effects on students and the consequences of stress are quite harmful. The outcomes of stress include suicide, violence, taking drugs, aggressive acts, and self-destruction which should be taken into account. For student’s life, stress acts as a great warning to their worth of life. So, it is the moral duty of the authorities of all institutions to protect their young students from facing stress and take positive steps to reduce these stressors. The solution to all these problems is in one word that is balance (Deng, et al., 2022).

As described earlier the outcomes of academic stress in which one of the most important is suicide. Attitude towards suicide is also the second variable of the current research. Suicide is defined as “the murderer to oneself, nothing other than a sort of withdrawal, an act, an end to psychic conflicts”. Suicide is a conscious act of self-inflicted ending. Suicidal ideations are suicidal thoughts or ideas or thinking (Yoyen & Keles, 2024).

Attitude towards suicide is defined as a “predisposition to some class of stimuli with cognitive, affective, and behavioral responses, conceptualizes suicide as persistent positive or negative emotion” (Diaz et al., 2023). Different kinds of attitudes towards suicide were found. Some youngsters were opposing suicide and taking it as a sin and so their attitude towards suicide becomes negative. Some people view that we should focus on the problem that is causing suicide, other adolescents view it that we should understand the condition of the person who had suicidal threats and then oppose him or her if possible (Choi & Soe, 2011). Destructive attitude towards self and or attitude towards suicidal behavior are incorporated under stressful conditions and become a separate and discrete alien part of the personality (Okechukwu et al., 2022). Academic stress is becoming the major cause of committing suicide among college students

(Urme et al., 2022); children committing suicide were both expecting and receiving punishment from school or their parents. She noted that children use jumping from heights as common suicidal method (Imran et al., 2023).

Whenever a person is confronted with an ill structured problem and become unable to get solution, he decides to commit suicide. It is also found that culture is also responsible, inadequate environment, presence of rifles, decline in religious attitudes, absence of both parents, aggression, lack of self esteem and self worth, different stresses and depression (Estrada et al., 2019). Those adolescents who have parents with anxiety and depression are more vulnerable towards suicide. Other things that can cause suicide might be loss of employment, financial losses, and sometime an unknown cause can lead towards suicide (Liu & Wang, 2024).

Different theories of suicide have been proposed. According to the theory given by Baumeister (2000) some suicides come up with the strong urge to flee from the bad self-awareness in the form of hurting feelings of lack of success (Yoyen & Keles, 2024). According to the theory of Linehan and Shearin different mental-health authorities have concluded that suicide is considered as a solution to any problem which is creating frustration (Yoyen & Keles, 2024). According to the theory of Shneidman (as cited in Davison & Neale, 2001), suicide is a mindful effort to solve a problem that is producing intense misery. To the sufferer, this solution ends consciousness and endurable pain. Beck explained hopelessness-helplessness theory in which he says that a person feels helplessness when become depressed (Baryshnikov & Isometsa, 2022).

A lot of work has been done on finding out the relationship of academic stress and suicide. In one qualitative research, Bashir (2011) had interviewed two of the intermediate students who have committed suicide but they were rescued. In interview, one of the participants mentioned his reason behind suicide that he had not get admission in medical college and it was the most traumatic experience of his life after which he had committed suicide This clearly depicts the relationship between academic stress and suicide.

Different researchers explored in their work that there is an influence of academic pressure on students which led them to the mental health problems. The

studies revealed that academic stress is a problem that is facing by the students. Particular quantity of stress is a good thing for success but when this stress became rigorous it leads toward mental health problems. Significant association between academic stress and mental health problems that is depression as well as suicidal ideation has been found. The association between academic stress and suicidal thoughts was also found to be considerable. The relationship among academic stress, depression and suicidal ideation was also found significant (Abdullah et al., 2024; Barbayannis et al., 2022; Iqra, 2024).

School and family also contribute a lot in causing depression and suicide ideation in adolescents. Different researchers revealed that suicide ideation was significantly related with depression, test anxiety, academic self-concept, and adolescents perceived parental dissatisfaction with academic performance (Kwon et al., 2023; Steare et al., 2023; Windarwati et al., 2022). Academic related issues, dysfunctional behavior, educational institute related stress, family environment and low self-esteem and socioeconomic factors predicted suicidal behavior in adolescents (Deng, et al., 2022).

Adolescent suicide is a worldwide problem but nowadays in our country the ratio of committing suicide is increasing day by day. As the world is progressing by leaps and bounds and education is a vital factor for the progress so academic stress is also increasing accordingly. With the increase in the competition students have become more sensitive towards studies especially intermediate students. Parent's expectations and self expectations leads to academic stress and when these expectations are not fulfilled, it results in aggressive acts like suicide (Hink et al., 2022; Imran et al., 2023). So, the current research aims to investigate the intensity of academic stress in intermediate students and how much of it is transformed into the attitude toward suicide. The results will enhance our understanding of the troubles of the students regarding academics and help the higher authorities, information centers, and members of administration in reducing the adverse effects of stress. It was hypothesized that

1. Science intermediate students would have more academic stress and attitude towards suicide than arts intermediate students.

2. There would be a significant positive relationship between academic stress and attitude towards suicide in science and arts students.

Methods

Research design

A cross-sectional research design is used in this study.

Sample

A convenient sampling technique was used to collect the sample. The sample consisted of 120 male intermediate students (science students=60, arts students=60). Their age ranges between 17 to 19 years ($M= 17.4$, $SD= .57$). Data was collected from the two government colleges of Lahore.

Assessment measures

Demographic Information Questionnaire

Demographic information questionnaire was used to get information about age, number of siblings, family system (nuclear, joint), student's status (day scholar, hostelite) and family structure with reference to presence of parents (both parent, single parent/guardian).

Educational Stress Scale for Adolescents (ESSA).

The scale used to measure academic stress was the Educational Stress Scale for the Adolescents (ESSA), which consists of 16 items. Higher score indicated a higher level of academic stress. Cronbach's alpha of ESSA scale was .81, indicating good internal consistency. The test-retest reliability was .78. The permission for using this tool was taken from the respected authors through mail (Dunne et al., 2010).

Attitude towards Suicide Questionnaire (ATTS)

This scale was used to measure Attitude towards suicide. The original scale contained 37 items and with the permission of the author, there had been

made some amendments in the tool according to the purpose of the current research. The tool was reviewed by four psychologists to categorize its items in positive or negative attitudes towards suicide and neutral items. Then, only those items were selected on which psychologists have consensus as being positive or negative items. All the neutral items were excluded and who were ambiguous for categorizing as positive or negative. The negative items selected were then reverse scored. Reliability for the ATTS questionnaire was .61 indicating moderate internal consistency (Renberg & Jacobsson, 2003).

Procedure

First of all, permission for using the tools was taken from the authors of the tools through mail. Then a short pilot study was conducted to check the understanding and ease of the students regarding questionnaires. It was found considerable. Then, with the permission from the department and concerned authority of public sector colleges, the researcher approached 11 public sector colleges of Lahore one by one for data collection. Equal distribution for science and arts students was taken from all colleges. Concerned authorities of all colleges permitted for data collection. Then the researcher approached 131 students and 120 students responded. Consent form and demographic questionnaire was first filled in by the participants. Then educational stress scale for adolescents (ESSA) and attitude towards suicide (ATTS) questionnaire was administered on the students. Questionnaires were administered in group settings in the class rooms of colleges. The researcher checked all the questionnaires at the spot and requested those students who left some of the questions to complete their questionnaires.

Results

Table I

Reliability of Questionnaires

Questionnaires	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of items
ESSA	.74	16
ATTS	.74	37

Note: ATTS= Attitude towards suicide questionnaire, ESSA= Educational stress scale for adolescents. Table I shows that the reliability of both the questionnaires was .74 which was satisfactory.

Table 2
Frequency distribution of academic stress and attitude towards suicide in science and arts students combined.

Variables	Intermediate students		Total
	Science	Arts	
	f(%)	f(%)	
Family System Nuclear	45(75)	15(25)	60
Joint	26(43)	34(57)	60
Academic Stress High	28(54)	23(46)	51
Academic Stress Low	32(46)	37(54)	69
Attitude towards suicide High	30(55)	25(45)	55
Attitude towards suicide Low	30(45)	35(55)	65

Table 2 shows the overall number of students who had high or low academic stress and attitude towards suicide. Independent sample t-test was to explore the differences in science students and arts students in terms of academic stress and attitude towards suicide.

Table 3
Comparison of science and arts students on level of academic stress, attitude towards suicide and demographic variables (N=120)

Variable	Science students (n=60)		Arts students (n=60)		t	p	95% CL	
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL
Academic Stress	59.90	7.61	50.33	7.57	3.05	.003**	-4.17	1.31
Attitude towards suicide	68.08	10.37	60.93	7.96	3.18	.004**	-6.19	.49

**p< .01

The results of the independent sample t-test indicated that science students would have a higher level of academic stress and attitude towards suicide than arts students.

Pearson product-moment correlation was used to explore the relationship between academic stress and attitude towards suicide in the art group and science group separately.

Result of the Pearson product-moment correlation indicated that academic stress significantly positively correlated with attitude towards suicide in art intermediate students ($r=.26, p<.05$). Moreover, it also indicated that academic stress significantly positively correlated with attitude towards suicide in science intermediate students ($r=.52, p<.05$) with stronger correlation in science group.

Discussion

This paper looked at the relationship between academic stress and attitude towards suicide in science and arts intermediate students. As we have discussed earlier that stress leads to an attitude towards suicide but we did not find that in our research. So, we will now look at the factors that might be the reasons of such results. We will discuss them with reference to both hypotheses.

According to the first hypothesis that there would be a positive relationship between academic stress and attitude towards suicide in science and arts students, the findings of the study were aligned with the hypothesis and earlier findings (Abdullah et al., 2024; Barbayannis et al., 2022; Bashir, 2011; Iqra, 2024) which indicated the relationship among academic stress, depression and suicidal ideation was also found significant.

Religion, culture, spirituality, race, ethnicity, and a person's individual personality and mindset play a significant role in any person's attitude towards suicide. Different researchers also comply with the importance of the religion, culture, spirituality, and personality. Gearing and Lizardi (2009) found that practice guidelines play an important role in a person's tendency to commit suicide. The people who have the religion Islam and they are very much prone to the teachings of Islam are more likely to oppose suicide. The students taken for the current study have the religion Islam which always teaches that suicide is a sin. So, it may be possible that the students taken for this study have high level of religiosity due to which they have opposing attitude towards suicide.

Another factor contributing towards a person's attitude towards suicide is may be the role of peculiar personality traits of an individual. Research has also shown that personality traits affect person's attitude towards suicide. It may contribute in enhancing or reducing his attitude. It has been revealed that the people having traits of conduct problems and identity problems are more vulnerable towards suicidal thoughts as well as suicidal attempts (Brezo, paris, trembley, Vitaro, Zoccolillo, Hebert & turecki, 2006). As personality traits were not measured in the current research, so certain personality traits may be overpowering those students which have decreased their vulnerability to suicide. Socioeconomic factors, race and ethnicity have also considerable effect on the attitude towards suicide (Leo, 2002). It is also understandable that nowadays, world has progressed a lot and so many opportunities lie right in front of students instead of just being doctors and engineers. Students have many other future prospects and therefore, they do not feel stress to such an extent that it leads to suicide.

The second hypothesis was also that the students of science and arts intermediate group differ on academic stress and attitude towards suicide which is consistent with the literature (Deng et al., 2022; Imran et al., 2023). The level of stress can be that every student chooses subjects according to his or her own mental capacity and interest and they did not take stress. Academic commitments, financial crises, and lack of the ability to manage time, and procrastination actually cause stress and when a person perceives this stress as negative and becomes unmanageable, then it

affects both health and performance (Deng et al., 2022).

To summarize, we can say that academic stress increases the risk of attitude towards suicide in intermediate students.

Implications

1. This research will help school counselors and educational psychologists in looking towards the issues of students and making intervention plans for them.
2. It assists us in understanding that although the students of public sector colleges suffer from academic stress yet the tendency towards suicide is less because of their moral upbringing.
3. Additionally, if we see any suicide case, we should not neglect other reasons which may have caused it other than academic stress.

Limitations and recommendations

In this research, a comparison was done only between science and arts groups; in the future it was recommended that a more detailed breakdown of the groups be done to explore more comparisons. More aspects as religion, personality, parenting, and attachment, will be explored in future research for a comprehensive picture of attitude towards suicide.

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